

A framework for cultural/organisational compassion in healthcare: a systematic review protocol

Anticipated or actual start date

August 14, 2022

Anticipated completion date

September 30, 2023

Stage of review at time of this submission

Preliminary searches and piloting of the study selection process are completed.
Title/abstract screening process are completed.

Type

Systematic Review

Searches

To assess the available literature and the keywords used, preliminary searches were conducted prior by a review member (CLN) and discussed with another review member (TFF). A full search strategy for the following bibliographic databases: EMBASE (Ovid), CINAHL, PsycINFO (Ovid), ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global, and Scopus are conducted by CLN and TFF; both keyword and free text searches using proximity operator 3. There are no restrictions on the literature (other than written in English, Danish, Norwegian or Swedish). Only published literature are included.

Review questions

What does it take to become a compassionate health organisation? Which interventions foster cultural/organisational compassion among health professionals in hospitals, hospices, and general practices?

Domain being studied

Compassion means “to suffer together” and is defined as the feeling that arises when you are confronted with another’s suffering and feel motivated to relieve that suffering through action. There is a growing interest in compassion in healthcare, as compassion has proven to enhance the well-being of health professionals, patient outcomes, and the quality of healthcare services offered to patients and their relatives. Most studies, including systematic reviews, have addressed the impact of compassion at the individual level. The right environmental circumstances, however, influence the ability to cultivate compassion for the individual health professional. Therefore, this review focus on evidence of compassion-based (empathy, sympathy, kindness, and generosity) interventions addressed at a cultural/organisational level within healthcare.

Participants/population

Health professionals (with direct patient contact) within healthcare organisation; defined as hospitals, hospices, and general practices. Students are excluded from this review.

Intervention(s)/exposure(s)

Interventions that aim to create cultural/organisational compassion (empathy, sympathy, kindness, and generosity), e.g. creating compassionate values and visions, the leaders’ role in supporting compassion practices within the workplace, and compassion training for the individuals/groups.

Comparator(s)/control

None.

Types of studies to be included

Any type of interventions (mixed methods, quantitative, qualitative, (non-)randomised control trials, pilot studies, etc) focusing on cultural/organisation compassion (sympathy, empathy, kindness, generosity) within healthcare settings will be included in this review.

Context

Studies addressing compassion (empathy, sympathy, kindness, and generosity) interventions among healthcare professionals in hospitals, hospices, and general practices will be included. Settings with no direct patient contact are excluded.

Main outcomes

The effect of cultural/organisational compassion (empathy, sympathy, kindness, and generosity) on the health organisation; work environment and well-being among staff to be able to create a framework for conducting a compassionate organisation/culture.

Data extraction

Following the search, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into EndNote and then Covidence, and duplicates removed. Following the pilot test, 1) titles and 2) abstracts will be screened by four independent reviewers for assessment against the inclusion criteria for the review. The full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria by independent reviewers. Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence in full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer. The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final review.

Additional outcome(s)

None.

Data extraction (selection and coding)

Following the search, all identified citations will be collated and uploaded into EndNote and then Covidence, and duplicates manually removed by a reviewer (CLN). First, four reviewers (CLN, LNK, CT, and CLL) will independently and blind to each other screen records based on the title and secondly, based on the abstract for assessment against the inclusion criteria for the review. The full text of selected citations will be assessed in detail against the inclusion criteria as well as quality assessment (see below) by all four independent reviewers (CLN, LNK, CT, and CLL). Reasons for exclusion of sources of evidence in full text that do not meet the inclusion criteria will be recorded and reported in the review. Any disagreements that arise between the reviewers at each stage of the selection process will be resolved through discussion, or with an additional reviewer.

The results of the search and the study inclusion process will be reported in full in the final review. Two reviewers (CLN and CT) will independently and blind to each other use a Microsoft Excel spreadsheet to extract data from all the eligible articles. Here, the study characteristics (study design, methods used, participant characteristics, type of intervention, and results), and basic information (title, authors, journal name, publication year, and the country in which the study was carried out) will be collected. If any inconsistencies arise, these are discussed until an agreement between the two researchers, or with an additional reviewer. Missing data will be reported as missing in the spreadsheet.

Risk of bias (quality) assessment

Two reviewers (CLN and CT) will evaluate the individual sources of evidence included using the Critical Appraisal Skills Programme (CASP). The assessment of risk of bias will be done at the study level, evaluating the methods used and internal validity. If disagreements, a third reviewer will be involved

Strategy for data synthesis

A thematic analysis will be used to synthesise the data (if possible, we will conduct a meta-analysis). The aim is to create a framework based on the evidence. This aims to guide healthcare organisations in regard to creating a compassionate culture/organisation within their clinical practice.

Two review members (CLN and CT) will code the sample independently and meet to compare and reach an agreement. The codes will be grouped into a framework of descriptive themes. More review team members (JC, LNK, CLL, and TFF) will be invited into the discussion to reach an overall agreement to ensure trustworthiness.

Analysis of subgroups or subsets

None.

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Conflicts of interest

None.